

CREATION OF A PEACEFUL FOREIGN POLICY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS POLITICAL AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655093>

Abstract. This article describes the multilateral cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan within the framework of international organizations. In particular, the economic, political and cultural cooperation relations, and the rapid development of the country's foreign relations in these areas to date are highlighted with specific dates.

Keywords: Multilateral relations, peaceful foreign policy, political and legal foundations, Central Asia, foreign policy concept.

In the last years of the last century, major changes and major global events took place in the Central Asian region. New sovereign, independent states were formed in the Central Asian region. This led to changes in the world political map. In the Central Asian region, newly independent states such as Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan developed and implemented their own new development path and national development models. The most important priority task for each of the states that were just starting to develop independently was regional security, peace and sustainable development. One of the most important priorities of the foreign policy of the Central Asian states, including Uzbekistan, is to ensure regional security and stability, and to combat any form of terrorism that threatens the peace of nations [1].

The history of human development shows that no state or society has developed in isolation. On the contrary, as soon as it chose the path of independent development, it joined the world community, developed multilateral cooperation, and boldly climbed the ladder of development.

From the very first days of independence, the issues of determining a sound foreign policy path consistent with Uzbekistan's national interests, joining the world community, and establishing political, diplomatic, economic, scientific, technical, and cultural ties with foreign countries were cross-cutting as urgent tasks. These were not easy tasks to solve. The complexity of the issue was that during the Union period, foreign policy, communication with the outside world, and the organization of foreign trade were carried out by Moscow, the central government. The republics, including Uzbekistan, were closed countries isolated from the outside world and unable to communicate directly. Therefore, our state did not have the experience of conducting foreign policy, nor personnel familiar with world diplomacy and foreign economic activity. There was not a single educational institution in the republic that could train such personnel. The situation urgently required the formation of foreign political and foreign economic relations.

In the works of the First President of our Republic Islam Karimov, such as "Uzbekistan's path to independence and development" [2], "Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: security threats, conditions for stability and guarantees of development" [3], "Uzbekistan is on the path of deepening economic reforms", "Uzbekistan is striving for the 21st century" [4], "16-year independent development path of Uzbekistan", "High spirituality is an invincible force"

and “Our main goal is to democratize and renew society, modernize and reform the country”, “Further deepening democratic reforms in our country and strengthening civil society”

The peace-loving foreign policy of our country, which is in line with the peace and security of the peoples of the world, ensured its rapid recognition as an independent state in the world. The state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan was recognized by influential countries of the world, with many of which diplomatic, political, economic, scientific-technical and cultural relations were established.

So, from the scientific conclusions presented, it is clear that only an independent free society can fully manifest itself, including in the framework of international relations. Independent Uzbekistan will successfully pass this school again. Now, the state of Uzbekistan, standing on the great platform of the world community, is showing activity and initiative in solving global problems of the world.

The foreign policy concept of Uzbekistan was developed on the basis of generalizing the national experience accumulated in our country in foreign policy over the past years of independent development, as well as in-depth study of the experience of advanced foreign countries [5]. It embodies the medium- and long-term strategic goals and objectives of our country's foreign policy, taking into account the complex characteristics of the current era.

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